

IMPACT OF HYDROCARBON PRODUCTION ON THE PRESSURE REGIME OF GEOTHERMAL RESERVOIRS IN THE SOUTHERN HUNGARIAN GREAT PLAIN

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ABSTRACT: *The Pannonian sea sediments (Alföld and Dunántúl Group), which are located in the compaction anticline at a depth of 1600-2600 m around Szeged (South Hungarian Great Plain), contain more than 70 oil and gas reservoirs. The sediments of the Dunántúl Group also serve as a geothermal reservoir, tapped by a growing number of thermal wells. Since the sandy layers of the sedimentary basin are hydraulically connected both horizontally and vertically. If the pressure in the pores is changed at one point, the resulting pressure changes can be observed throughout the basin, as confirmed by interaction studies carried out in 1986 and again in 2010.*

Based on the water level data of the Szeged thermal system and the thermal wells of the Southern Great Plain, it can be concluded that the area under investigation has experienced a drop in the water level of almost 100 m over the last 50 years, which cannot be explained by the production of thermal water alone. Hydrocarbon production from horizontal and vertical wells may be responsible for a significant part of the anomalies.

A regional-scale, high-resolution groundwater flow model was built to investigate the effects of hydrocarbon and thermal water production and to determine the extent of the interaction.

Our results show that the impact of production wells is negligible, with hydrocarbon mining causing a much larger depression, only slightly influenced by the production of geothermal systems.

Key words: *Pannonian Basin, geothermal energy, hydrocarbon production, delta sediments*

INTRODUCTION

Europe is accelerating the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy. In 2015, the European Commission launched the Energy Union strategy to boost energy security, creating a fully integrated internal energy market, improving energy efficiency, decarbonising the economy and supporting research innovation and competitiveness. Geothermal energy is widely known for its reliable, weather-independent and renewable nature, and it is well suited for these purposes. Every geothermal system needs a heat source, a reservoir and a working fluid. A good reservoir is permeable and fractured sedimentary or volcanic rocks, where fluid in the pores flows freely, allowing for easy extraction and refill. Pore space, also known as porosity, is the part of the rock containing the liquid and gaseous phases of the rock. Geothermal energy exploitation, a form of pore space management. Pore space is, in addition to the above, utilised hydrocarbon production and storage, CO₂ disposal, heat storage. However these utilisations, especially hydrocarbons and thermal water are found in the same reservoir and their production affects each other. So the value of pore space as a usable finite volume is expected to increase significantly in the future (Hámorné-Vidó et al. 2021). This is particularly true for porous sandstone reservoirs in the Pannonian Basin.

Geological overview

Geologically, the Pannonian Basin is a complex extensional basin system of Neogene age overlying several Mid-Cretaceous to Paleogene age sub-basins consisting of Mesozoic and Paleozoic rocks. These structural sub-basins are filled by Neogene and Quaternary sediments ranging in thickness from less than 100 m to greater than 7,000 m from surface to the top of basement. During the Miocene, while the surrounding mountains were uplifting under compression, the Pannonian Basin was subsiding under extension and rifting. The pelagic marine sediments (Alföld Group) deposited to the basement (formerly the Lower Pannonian), which were formed during the relatively quiet geological periods following the late Miocene regression. This period was followed by a period of rather violent subsidence and structural movements. Its sediments belong to the Dunántúl Group (formerly the Upper Pannonian) (Szatnó & Tari 1993, Horváth et al 2006). Along the basin margin, the sedimentation environment was characteristically near-shore, with predominantly delta sediments (Révész 1980).

Since the beginning of last century, 270 oil and 690 gas deposits have been discovered in Hungary, with the most significant hydrocarbon occurrence in the southern part of the Pannonian Basin, in the Szeged area. The Late Miocene basin sediments overlying the Algyó Ridge contain more than 70 oil and gas plays at depths between 1600-2500 m (Kiss et al. 2015)(Fig 1).

Fig 1. Geological section of the hydrocarbon field near Szeged, with location of the study area. Legend: blue: reservoir, red: gas field, green: oil field (Based on Kiss et al. 2015)

Hydrogeological background

There are two vertically stacked major groundwater flow systems within the Pannonian Basin: an upper “gravity-driven” flow system, and a lower “overpressured” flow system (Almási, 2001; Tóth & Almási, 2001). The base of the uppermost gravity flow system is the bottom of the Újfalú Formation (formerly the upper Pannonian bottom). Starting from the Algyó Formation (formerly the lower Pannonian top), significant overpressures of up to 40 MPa can occur. The transition between the two flow systems is often sharp, with pressure rises of up to 15-20 MPa at 10-20 m (Almási, 2001)

The distribution of porosity and permeability in the deltaic sediments of the basin varies greatly with the sandstone/rock ratio and depth. The hydraulic properties of each layer cannot be described by a single value due to the heterogeneous rock composition and structural discontinuities, but can be estimated from the rock composition [10]. The regional hydraulic connectivity for the Alföld Group varies between 10^{-9} - 10^{-6} m/s, and for the Dunántúl Group it is 10^{-5} m/s [10]. The majority of hydrocarbon plays and thermal wells in the study area are situated by the same aquifers, and their spatial distribution is shown in Fig 2.

Fig 2. The location of hydrocarbon plays (yellow) and thermal water wells (red) in the study area. The upper surface is the base of the Quaternary Formations, while the lower surface is the boundary between Dunántúl Group and Alföld Group

FLUID PRODUCTION

The discovery of the hydrocarbon fields between 1965 and 1972 added more than 100 million tonnes of oil and 120 Bcm³ of gas (excluding the Makó trough) to the geological reserves of the Szeged Basin. About half of Hungary's total hydrocarbon production is attributable to the fields of the Szeged Basin. The exploitation of hydrocarbon fields used have created significant local and regional pressure level changes in the thermal reservoirs of the Southern Great Plain (Völgyi 1970, Kiss et al. 2015). Since hydrocarbon extraction became significant from 1970 the pressure in the aquifer prior to this date can be characterised by a different gradient from the pressure gradient determined from wells drilled after 1970. In the Dunántúl Group, the pressure decreased by 0.9 MPa between 1965 and 2010 (Szanyi & Pinjung 2017).

In the past, the production of thermal water in the region was mainly for agricultural and partly balneological purposes. Currently, the city is undergoing very significant geothermal development to supply geothermal energy for district heating, with 9 production wells and 18 reinjection wells.

GROUNDWATER FLOW MODEL

In order to simulate as realistically as possible, the production of hydrocarbon deposits and thermal water wells, a high-resolution transient model was created using Visual Modflow software, which was divided into annual time periods covering the period 1965-2002. The initial hydrogeological parameters of the model were based on literature data and results from backfilling studies of thermal wells and were refined after repeated calibrations of the model.

During hydrocarbon production, water leaks into the reservoirs from the vicinity of the reservoirs due to pressure drop, causing local depression in the aquifers [3]. Hydrocarbon reservoirs in the modelled area were incorporated into the model as polygons with potential levels corresponding to known reservoir and confining pressures, with pressure values maintained in the polygon areas by GHB cells. At the periphery of the hydrocarbon reservoirs, the deltaic system developed clayey-hydrocarbon-silty low permeability and low porosity formations that reduce water flow to the reservoirs. The presence of this assemblage was taken into account when determining the strength of GHB cells at the margins of hydrocarbon reservoirs, and the elastic layer parameters (e.g. storage factor) around the reservoirs were altered.

CONCLUSION

The impact of production wells is negligible, with mining causing a much larger depression, slightly affected locally by the production of geothermal systems. It still has to be reinjection of used fluid. In many areas of abandoned hydrocarbon production, a slow rise in potential levels can be seen.

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